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**An Analytical Study of Choice Factors of Prospective Students for
Selecting a B-School for Higher Studies**

By

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**A Research Paper
on
An Analytical Study of Choice Factors of Prospective Students for
Selecting a B-School for Higher Studies**

ABSTRACT

In the context of higher education ,especially business management education in India, a noticeable trend has been the increasing competition among B-Schools to attract students both locally and internationally. Competitive pressure has forced the B-schools to look for more aggressive marketing strategies in order to reach to and enthuse the prospective students to enroll in the respective B-School . This research paper is aimed to identify the choice factors that significantly persuade or impact the students in their selection of a B-School. It may be stated that research study outcomes may be useful and beneficial in terms of making the decision and will contribute to the functions that facilitate the B-Schools to plan and improve the choice factors for prospective students.

KEYWORDS

Higher Education, B-School, Choice Factors, Management Education.

Introduction

Over a period of time, Indian management education industry has grown in many folds; it is even becoming global by way of seeking overseas associations. This has intensified the competition in management education sector and thus it has become increasingly turbulent. With much more players and intensified competition we are witnessing advent of more B-Schools. Varying needs and requirements of management education both in the domestic and global market has prompted the development of such market culture amongst business schools.

B-schools are now in a position where they have to compete for scarce resources such as finances. To survive in this competitive environment, institutions must have an advantage. This means that a business management institution must provide its target market with more value than its competitors. In order to provide superior value to the students, management education institutions need to anticipate and take into consideration student's needs and their choice factors in selecting a B-school.

Considering all the challenges that management education institutions are faced with, it is evident that B-Schools need to focus increasingly on marketing techniques used by other professional organizations. One of the key issues in the successful development of a suitable marketing strategy is to determine which factors students consider when they have to make a decision on which B-Schools to enroll at. They make a proper assessment of the prospective institute by using all sources of information so that they utilize their time, money and other resources optimally, not taking a chance to lament on loss at any point of time

Literature emphasizes the need for management education institutions to identify the choice factors and various sources of information used by students, in order to understand their customers better.

The main objective of this study is therefore to investigate the relative importance of choice factors considered by the students before enrollment at business management institutions.

Choice Factors

Choice factors are nothing but the characteristics of B-Schools which the students look at before enrolling themselves. According to various studies and literature reviews, these are broad features the B-schools promote and may vary from institution to institution. These factors and their nomenclature are differ from each other.

Some of the examples as mentioned by the review of literature are as listed below:

- One study found out the factors that Indian students prefer while selecting the B-School. The study focuses on the student's decision-making activity and lists some factors. These are additional academic things, eligibility criteria, course content offerings, physical facilities, individual preferences, and affiliation or endorsement.
- The second study found that the socio-economic status of the students and parents has considerable effect on the type of university in which the students wish to study. It also shows that students are satisfied with the institution that is based on their choice and provide information satisfaction with respect to academic recognition (external influence).
- Yet another study lists some factors that influence a person's decision to go to college. These are: career opportunities, financial stability, social recognition, intellectual status, and self-respect.
- One more investigation reveals that the overall, individual factors (such as personal inclination, future scope, work-life balance) were rated as more important than professional factors (such as work variations and work related preferences) while pursuing higher education.

- Another researcher has suggested that the most considerable aspect mentioned by both male and female student was assurance for placement and the institution ranking.

Thus, from the above , we can summarize and arrive at a selective list of choice factors , which are as follows:

- Placements
- Recognition / Fame
- Physical Facilities / Infrastructure in Place
- Specialization
- Faculty / Teaching
- Peer Counsel
- Fees Structure
- Alumni Base
- Location
- Accreditation
- Residential Campus
- Financial Help
- Industry Connections
- Research Orientation
- Collaboration with Overseas Educational Institutes

Objective:

The broad objective of this research paper study is to identify and examine the important choice factors considered by the students before they enroll at business management institutions.

Empirical Research Results

Although education brings behaviour changes in individuals but the benefits of education are multidimensional, which particularly serve the broader national interests. Today the expectations of the students and their parents are too high while selecting the B-Schools.

The present study was undertaken by collecting data from the prospective post graduate students aspiring to enroll in B –Schools for higher studies in business management education. The findings of the study indicated that there are several factors that influence students' decision. It was found that the main factors which affect the student's decisions are extracurricular / student's activities, faculty, placement industry-institute, University results, facilities and financial aids, location and feedback from the alumni.

Factors and sub-factors considered for the survey are as shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Factors and Sub-Factors

Sr. No.	Factors	Sub-Factors
I	Extracurricular Activity, Faculty and Placement	Extracurricular/Students events Number and qualities of faculty Brand image Industrial link of the institute Institution Ranking Renowned and Experience Faculty Good placement record Good placement facilities
II	University Results and Affiliations	Overall teaching Good university results Good study environment Accreditation/Affiliation
III	Facilities & Resources	Online fee payment, online results facility Communication Facilities Financial Aids/scholarships Specialization

		Admission procedure Fee structure
IV	Social Factors and Others	Nearer to my home Existing students/number of students Alumni College Representative Advertisement
V	Infrastructure	Good Infrastructure Campus Visit Residential Campus Maximum operation hours of Library College hostel and its facilities
VI	Foreign Tours	Foreign Tours facility Collaboration with foreign institute
VII	Compelling Circumstances	Family culture/tradition Others remark (Friends/Relatives) Elder's suggestion Discipline in students

The researcher had collected the data from the survey respondents.

Study results of the field survey are as follows:

The scores for various factors (as revealed from the survey) are as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Factors and their Scores

Sr. No.	Factors	Sum	Average
I	Extracurricular Activity, Faculty and Placement	7.395	0.924
II	University Results and Affiliations	3.687	0.922
III	Facilities & Resources	5.563	0.927
IV	Social Factors and Others	4.395	0.879
V	Infrastructure	4.403	0.881

VI	Foreign Tours	1.612	0.806
VII	Compelling Circumstances	3.232	0.808

Within these major factors top ranked sub-factors and their scores are given below. [Figure 1 to Figure 7]

Figure 1: Top Ranked Sub-Factors [Factor I]

Extracurricular Activity, Faculty and Placement

As shown above, the top sub-factors are Extracurricular/Students events, Number and qualities of faculty, Brand image and Industrial link of the institute.

Figure 2: Top Ranked Sub-Factors [Factor II]

University Results and Affiliations

As shown above, the top sub-factors are Overall teaching, Good university results and Good study environment.

Figure 3: Top Ranked Sub-Factors [Factor III]

Facilities & Resources

As shown above, the top sub-factors are online fee payment, online results facility, Communication Facilities, Financial Aids/scholarships and Specialization.

Figure 4: Top Ranked Sub-Factors [Factor IV]

Social Factors and Others

As shown above, the top sub-factors are Nearer to my home, Existing students/number of students, Alumni and College Representative.

Figure 5: Top Ranked Sub-Factors [Factor V]

Infrastructure

As shown above, the top sub-factors are Good Infrastructure, Campus Visit, Residential Campus and Maximum operation hours of Library.

Figure 6: Top Ranked Sub-Factors [Factor VI]

Foreign Tours

As shown above, the top sub-factors are Foreign Tours facility and Collaboration with foreign institute.

Figure 7: Top Ranked Sub-Factors [Factor VII]

Compelling Circumstances

As shown above, the top sub-factors are Family culture/tradition, others remark (Friends/Relatives), and Elder's suggestion.

Study Implications

It was seen that the decision factors assume essential part in enlistment of the students. It must be noted that understanding of the significance of decision making factors that the students use to make their selection of B-School, can helps marketer. The findings could also impact on communication, marketing and recruitment strategy of B-Schools

The decision factors which the students showed as minimum imperative it doesn't imply that the B-School ought to overlook the same, however B-school ought to be center their showcasing key on the genuine customers of students.

It is required to look into other aspects of the student decision-making process, including personal factors, family background, academic achievements, and other considerations. The causal relationship between college choice and post-purchase behaviour, academic achievements, and satisfaction levels, can also be examined.

Similarly, more constructs can be defined and measured in follow-up studies. As this research is meant for exploratory purposes, it was believed that a wealth of other follow-up assignments may be undertaken. In particular, more studies in this field need to be conducted before a clearer picture of the education industry will emerge.

The above options clear out that B-School need to take some sort of action according to their unique situation & recourses availability.

Conclusions

The study finding showed that B-Schools must pay attention towards following impact factors:

- Extracurricular Activity, Faculty and Placement [Factor I]
- Facilities & Resources [Factor III] and
- Infrastructure [Factor V]

It may be observed that there were numerous differences in the finding from this study. It can further be concluded that parents and students belongs to different educational, economic & social background, as well as institutes they attended differ according to the importance they given to the different impact factors.

As above shows that the students market is not a homogeneous market and high listing the fact that B-School new to conditionally research there market to try and understand then potential consumers, i.e. students. The result further reveals that not all choice factors are equally important.

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